

Physico-Chemical Properties of Ala-River, Akure Ondo State, Nigeria. (A Case Study Ofala River in Akure, South Western Nigeria)

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ABSTRACT

Water is one of the most abundant compounds found in nature covering the largest part of the earth's surface. In spite of this apparent abundance, several factors tend to limit the amount of portable water available for human use. In this work, physico-chemical properties of water such as temperature, pH, colour, conductivity, hardness, chemical oxygen demand etc. as well as the concentration level of heavy metals and composition of effluents in Ala River was determined and analysed vis-à-vis W.H.O standard so as to determine its suitability or otherwise for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes. Results obtained indicate that most of the water parameters determined for Ala River were within the permissible limits stated by W.H.O for portable water, except for Mn, Ni, and Pb which are beyond the limits. Also, Chemical Oxygen Demand (C.O.D) is not high for samples (3.50-15.80), an indication that the water is not heavily contaminated with heavy organic matter. The presence of Cd, Hg was not detected in the water samples which make the water safe for various usages, though some degree of treatment is required to make it fit for consumption purpose.

Keywords: *Chemical Oxygen Demand, Conductivity, Heavy metals, pH, Physico-chemical properties*

INTRODUCTION

The availability of adequate water supply both in quality and quantity is essential for human existence. With the exponential increase in population, access to improved water remains an important pre-condition for sustaining human life, maintaining eco systems and for achieving sustainable development [1]. Also, industrial revolution has led to the development of many new and increasingly complex manufacturing plant and processes. This has significantly increased the amount of gases, solid and liquid wastes released into the environment thereby reducing access to improved water supply. Access to safe drinking water refers to percentage of total population of people using improved water drinking sources which include household connection, public stand pipe, bore hole, protected dug well, protected spring and rain water collection while improved water sources include: unprotected well, spring, river or pond, tanker truck water, vendor provided water etc [2] as cited by [3]. It is important to note that all natural water contain a variety of contaminants arising from erosion, leaching and weathering processes amongst others. Added to these natural contaminants are domestic and industrial wastes which are disposed off into surface water or large water

bodies. Water bodies are capable of taking certain amount of pollutants without severe effect because of dilution. This may however impair the suitability of such water for various uses [4]. Residents relied on Ala River in Akure, Ondo State as alternative water source for domestic purpose. However this River runs through the city and receives domestic waste as well as effluents from local industries. It is based on this that it is needful to carry out a physico-chemical analysis (analysis of the physical and chemical properties) of water from the River so as to monitor the level of pollution not only for health reasons but also for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes.

Water a clear colourless liquid with an insipid taste [5], has been identified as one of the most basic needs and prerequisite for health and sustainable development [3]. Chemically, pure water does not exist for any appreciable length of time in nature. Even while falling as rain, water picks up small amounts of gases, ions, dust and particulate matter from the atmosphere. It flows over through the surface layers of the earth it dissolves and carries with it some pollutants. In fact, socio-economic progress is impossible without adequate supply of improved water [6] because water

serves a unique purpose in agricultural, domestic, power generation, sports and recreation, transportation as well as in the manufacturing industry. In environments where highly toxic industrial and domestic wastes are disposed off by dumping in or on land, in water bodies, stream and rivers without consideration for aquatic life, dwellers and agricultural effects, water becomes a sure medium for transmission of diseases and heavy metal concentration. An examination of water quality is basically a determination of the presence of organisms, heavy metals, minerals and organic compounds contained in the water [7]. Water pollution has been defined as a situation in which water in its pure state undergoes natural or induced changes in its quality which renders it unusable or dangerous to food, human and animal health, industry, agriculture, fishing or leisure pursuit [8]. The main causes of water pollution are basically from sewages and industrial effluents. Sewage is the content of sewers and originates from domestic and commercial premises, lands, drains, industrial waste and sites. The largest volume of discharged waste is in the form of an effluent [8]. This is a term that describes any solid, liquid or gaseous products in treated or untreated conditions discharged from a process [8]. Industrial effluents may contain water, organic solvents, oils, suspended and dissolved solids as well as chemical compounds [8]. Heavy metals are introduced into water bodies through oil spillage, sewage effluents, auto emission, industrial activities such as mining and quarrying, canning, electroplating, rock weathering etc. [9], [10] [11].

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research is a case study of Ala River in Akure, Ondo State (South-Western, Nigeria). Water samples from the River were collected using clean polypropylene plastic container washed with 0.01% of HCl. The container was then washed again and rinsed several times with distilled water. Prior to collection of water samples at the site, the containers were rinsed with the water samples. Water samples were collected in different containers by dipping it into the River, allowing it to fill to the brim and immediately the containers were corked. Samples collected at five locations along Ala River were labeled A, B, C, D and E (Table 1). Deep freezing was used as the method of sample preservation since it allows only the least changes in the samples during storage and also made it unnecessary to add chemicals which could contaminate the samples.

ANALYSIS

Physico-chemical properties analysed include: Temperature, pH, Conductivity, Hardness etc. Test was also carried out to determine the presence of inorganic compounds and presence of heavy chemicals.

Temperature

The temperature of various samples was determined by dipping a thermometer calibrated in degree centigrade (00C) into the water and reading the corresponding temperature.

pH

The pH of the water samples was determined using Philips Model pw 9418 pH meter. After allowing the pH meter to warm up for about 15 minutes and dully calibrated with standard buffers pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0, the pH of the water was determined by dipping the electrode into the water samples.

Conductivity

Conductivity was determined using Bridge type M. C. 3 conductivity meter calibrated in

Hardness

To 100 ml of the water sample was added 2 ml of NH₄/NH₄Cl buffer to bring the pH value to 9.0. About 0.2 g of Erichrome black T indicator was added which formed a wine red colour. The whole content was stirred and titrated against 0.01 M EDTA to blue end point.

Hardness:

$$= \frac{0.01MofEDTA \times Titrationvalue \times molarmassofCaCO_3 \times 1000}{sample(ml)}$$

Presence of Chloride (Cl⁻)

Titrimetric method was employed in which 50 ml of the samples were titrated against a standard solution of 0.0257M silver nitrate (AgNO₃) solution with 1 ml solution of 5% K₂Cr₂O₇ as indicator to a reddish brown end point.

$$\text{Calculation: } Cl^-(\text{mg/L}) = \frac{(A - B) \times 35,400}{sample(ml)} \quad (2)$$

A=Volume of AgNO₃ used for sample titration

M=Molarity of AgNO₃ used

B= Volume of AgNO₃ used for blank titration

Presence of Sulphate

To 10 ml samples in 25 ml Erlenmeyer flask was added 5 ml of gelatin barium chloride. Stirring continued for 1 minute and stand for 30 minutes. A cloudy colour was observed. The absorbance was then determined at 420 nm by corning colorimeter 253. Standards ranging from 2ppm-10ppm SO₄²⁻ were prepared from sodium sulphate stock solution and treated as above. Sulphate concentration was read from the standard curve and results was calculated from the equation given as

$$\text{ppm/SO}_4^{2-} = \frac{mass(curve) \times 1000}{sample(ml)} \dots 3$$

Presence of Phosphate

4 ml of prepared ascorbic acid were pipette and 1.06 g of ascorbic acid was weighed and made up to 200 ml. The sample was added to make the required volume 50 ml. The solution was thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. A cloudy colour was observed. The absorbance was then determined at 420 nm using corning colorimeter 253. Readings of unknown were read from the standard curve and the result was calculated as follow:

$$Mg / L PO_4^{3-} = \frac{Curvereadings \times 1000 \times D}{Sample(ml)} \quad (4)$$

Where

D: Is the dilution factor.

Presence of Nitrate

10 ml of each sample were poured into an evaporating dish and evaporated to dryness using a hot plate at 1050C and allowed to cool after which 2 ml of phenol-2,4 disulphuric acid reagent were added to each evaporating dish. After 10 mins, 10 ml of distilled water were added to dilute each solution which was then transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. This was followed by the

addition of 200 ml of NH₄OH to make it alkaline and a yellow colour was developed. The content was finally made up to mark with distilled water. Then the absorbance of the yellow solution was measured at 460 nm using corning colorimeter 253. Standard were prepared from KN₃, with 10 ml diluted with 90 ml of distilled water to make 100 ppm.

Presence of Nitrite

The sample prepared was left overnight to oxidize and then the absorbance was read from the corning colorimeter and the concentration of the unknown was determined from the calibrating graph.

Determination of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

100 ml of the prepared sample was measured and titrated against sodium thiosulphate. The colour was observed from deep

yellow to light yellow and 2 drops of starch solution was added and the titration continued until it changes from blue to light yellow again.

Detection of Heavy Metals

The Presence of metals such as Cr, Hg, Pb, Mn, Cd and Ni was detected using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Standards were prepared for each metal using the salts of the metal. The instrument was switched on and the relevant hollow cathode lamp and wavelength fixed for each metal. Air acetylene flame was used. Standards of each metal were thereafter sprayed into the flame as well as the sample with their corresponding absorbance taken. Values for both the standards and samples were read under the same condition.

RESULTS

Table 1.0: Physico-chemical Properties of Ala River

S/N	PROPERTIES	SAMPLES					Mean value	W.H.O Standard [12]
		A	B	C	D	E		
1	Temperature (°C)	25.20	25.50	25.00	21.10	25.00	24.36	29.00
2	Colour	colourless	colourless	colourless	colourless	Colourless		colourless
3	Odour	odourless	odourless	odourless	odourless	Odourless		Odourless
4	Phosphate (mg/l)	2.00	3.00	4.00	1.40	8.00	3.68	0.40
5	Sulphate (mg/l)	300	200	600	800	100	400	400
6	Conductivity (µmhos)	0.95×10 ³	0.25×10 ³	0.29×10 ³	0.79×10 ³	0.21×10 ³	498	1.40×10 ³
7	pH	8.40	7.00	7.00	7.50	7.50	7.48	6.5-8.5
8	Nitrate (mg/l)	5.00	3.80	2.20	2.10	3.40	3.3	1.00
9	Nitrite (mg/l)	6.30	6.60	4.40	0.20	5.00	4.5	0.10
10	Chloride (mg/l)	4.10	9.20	7.40	28.30	10.27	11.85	250
11	Mg Hardness (mg/l)	0.50	4.00	4.00	14.00	8.00	6.1	500
12	Ca Hardness (mg/l)	16.00	8.00	4.80	8.00	8.00	8.98	500
13	C.O.D	11.30	15.80	9.10	11.40	3.50	10.22	NS

NS-No Specification

Fig. 1.0: Physico-chemical Properties for the collected samples

Fig. 2.0: Physico-chemical Properties (WHO standard)

Table 2.0: Concentration of Heavy Metals in Ala River

S/N	Metals	CONCENTRATION OF SAMPLES (mg/L)					Mean values	W.H.O Standard [12]
		A	B	C	D	E		
1	Pb	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.10	0.20	0.22	0.005
2	Cd	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND		0.10
3	Mn	6.50	4.50	3.10	0.90	1.10	3.22	0.001
4	Hg	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND		
5	Co	0.40	0.20	0.30	ND	0.10	0.25	0.10
6	Ni	1.10	0.50	1.00	0.60	1.40	0.92	

Fig. 3.0: Concentration of metals in mg/L for water samples

Fig. 4.0: Concentration of metals in mg/L (W.H.O standard)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of temperatures obtained for the different samples collected ranging from 21.10-25.500C are not too high for drinking and domestic use and are still within the acceptable limits of W.H.O standard. Water temperatures greater than 310C may impair the portability of the water, if they are to be used in industries for cooling purposes. Temperature was almost constant except for sample D (21.100C), its relatively low temperature may be due to the presence of shade caused by trees. The pH of the water samples (7.00-8.40) fell within the W.H.O limit (6.50-8.50). Values obtained slightly vary from those obtained by [13] [14] who recorded close to neutral pH for rural water supplies in Calabar and shallow wells in Akure respectively. Hence, in terms of this parameter, the water is suitable for its intended purpose. The conductivity results obtained for all the samples ranges between (0.21×103 µmhos-0.95×103 µmhos), they all fell within W.H.O standard which is 1.0×103 µmhos.

Chemical Oxygen Demand (C.O.D) is not high for samples (3.50-15.80) which indicate the water is not heavily contaminated with heavy organic matter. However, the range is high because organic matters are moved along as the water flows. The results obtained for phosphate (1.40-8.00 mg/l) are too high compared to W.H.O standard (0.4 mg/l) and are higher compared to the levels obtained by [14] [15] and [16]. This may be due to detergents with high phosphate content used in washing clothes. Phosphate values varied but least for sample D, which may be due to population density. The sulphate concentration in all the samples was between 100 and 800 mg/l. When compared with the W.H.O standard value (400 mg/l) [12], it means the water needs treatment. Sulphate is an important constituent of hardness as well as Ca and Mg. At higher levels, sulphate imposes bitter taste on water and can produce laxative effect on human [16]. From table 1.0, nitrate and nitrite have ranges of 2.10-5.00 and 0.20-6.60 respectively. The concentrations are higher compared to W.H.O standard. The finding is similar to results obtained by [16] [17]. This may be due to atmospheric nitrogen combining with rainfall during the season as well as decayed plant materials that get into the water. The concentration of chloride in all the samples is within the ranges of 4.10-28.30, which are very low and fell within the acceptable limit of 250 mg/l set by W.H.O. Ala River is far from the sea and hence not likely to be polluted by much chloride, besides, there is no factory producing table salt around Akure metropolitan. Results obtained in the present work for total hardness are below the W.H.O (1984) permissible limit for drinking water quality. In terms of water quality, the water is soft [18] [19]. Hardness ranges between 0-60.00 mg/l and 0-50.00 mg/l respectively suggest the water is soft. The water is soft. The water is suitable for drinking if treated and other

domestic purposes such as cleaning and washing because it forms lather easily with soap. The values obtained for Pb, Mn, and Ni are high compared with the acceptable limits of W.H.O. This is consistent with the findings of [20] who reported Iron, Manganese, Chromium and Nickel as the most abundant elements from coastal sediments of Ondo State. It is also similar with the finding during assessment of soil, water and plant pollution by heavy metals from petroleum and petrochemical companies in Nigeria [20]. Manganese is a well known neurotoxic metal responsible for physical and neurological disorders in exposed persons [21]. The chances of toxicity of these elements are enhanced by the large volume of water required daily by man. Hg and Cd were not detected in the samples. This is a sign of water

purity as both metals are very toxic and without any known biochemical importance.

CONCLUSION

This work revealed that most of the water parameters determined for Ala River were within the W.H.O (1984), permissible limit for portable water, except for Mn, Ni, and Pb which are beyond the limits. One interesting feature about the results is the fact that the heavy (toxic) metals Cd, Hg were not detected in the water samples. However, the low C.O.D means the water has not been contaminated with heavy organic and bacterial load from industry. Though some of the elements determined were within the limits set by W.H.O (1984), it is important to state that gradual accumulation of some metals within these limits over a period of time will cause health hazard on people and aquatic lives that depends on the water for survival. Therefore, water from Ala River will require some treatment to make portable but in its present form, it can be used for laundry. Since Ala River flows through Akure town, bacteriological analysis will be required if the water is to be purified for domestic use.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As a long term measure, it is pertinent to state that the use of contaminated water arises when wholesome water is not available hence the need to make clean and treated water available for the entire Nigerian populace. In the interim, the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) should ensure that all companies discharging effluents into Rivers and water ways should as a matter of deliberate policy treat their waste and ensure they meet the guidelines for effluents discharge into waters, while erring companies should be penalized.

People living along water ways should be properly enlightened of the possible dangers and health risk associated with the use of untreated water with a view of discouraging discharge of sewage and other domestic waste into water ways. Water from Ala River must be properly treated for drinking purpose.

REFERENCES

1. Schirmding, Y. V. (2000). 'Health in the Context of Agenda 21 and Sustainable Development: Meeting the Challenges of the 21st Century' Sustainable Development Int'; Strategies and Technologies for Agenda Implementation. ICG Publishing Ltd, U.K
2. WHO and UNICEF (2004.) Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation; Meeting the MDG Drinking Water and Sanitation Target: A Mid-Term Assessment of Progress, W.H.O Geneva.
3. Olajuyigbe, A. E. and J. O. Fasakin (2010). Some Factors Impacting on Access to Improved Sources of Domestic Water Supply in a Rapidly Urbanizing State Capital in South-Western Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Technology*. 1(1) 42-51.
4. Tebbut, T. H. Y (1983). *Principles of Water Quality Control*, 3rd Edition, Pergamal Press, England
5. Holdernes, A. and D. Lamberts (1983). *A New Certificate in Chemistry for Secondary Schools*, 6th Edition, Heinemann Educational Books Nigeria Ltd., Lagos.
6. NEST (1991): *Threatened Environment, A National Profile*. 1st Edition. A Publication of Nigeria Environmental

- Study/Action Team (NEST). Intec Printers Ltd, Ibadan, pp. 60-64.
7. Horreemoes, D. (1983). Stoichiometry Models for Examination of Extreme Pollution from Urban run offs. *Journal of Water Research* 22 (80): 1071-1026.
 8. Dix, H. M. C. (1981). *Environmental Pollution*. 1st Edition, Vail Ballon Press, USA, pp. 168-175.
 9. Marr, I. L. and M. S. Creaser (1983). *Environmental Chemical Analysis*. Blackie and Sons Publisher Ltd, 1ST Edition, pp. 104.
 10. Finerty, M. W., S. D. Madden, S. E. Feagley and R. M. Grodner (1990). "Metals in Drinking Water". *Arch. Environ. Contamination Toxicology* 19(1): 94-100.
 11. Guerrin, F. V., Bargat-Sacaze and P. De saqui-sannes (1990). Heavy Metals Pollution. *Bull Environ. Contamination Toxicology and Pollution with Heavy Metals*. *Nutr. Reports Int.* 38(6): 1157-1161.
 12. World Health Organization (1984). *Guidelines for Drinking Water*, Vol., 1. Geneva
 13. Itah, A. Y., S. M. Etukudoh and E. J. Akpan (1996). Bacteriological and Chemical Analysis of Some Rural Water Supplies in Calabar, Nigeria. *West African Journal of Biological and Applied Chemistry*. Vol., 41, pp. 1-9.
 14. Ipinmoroti, K. O. (1993). Water Quality of Shallow Wells Located Close to Dump Sites in Akure, Nigeria. *Pak Journal of Science and Industry*. Vol., 36, No 4, pp. 137-142.
 15. Udom, G. H., J. O. Etu-Efeotor and E. O. Esu (1991). Hydrochemical Evaluation of Ground Water in parts of Port-Harcourt and Tai Eleme Local Govt. Area in Rivers State. pp. 18-19
 16. Mathuthu, A. S., F. M. Zaranyika and S. B. Jonnalagodda (1993). Monitoring of Water Quality in Upper Mukivisi River In Harare, Zimbabwe *Environmental Int'l* . Pergerman Press, Ltd., USA Vol., 19 pp. 51-61
 17. Kataria H. C. (1988). Analysis of Drinking Water of Bhopal (Mp). *Ultra Science* 10(2):219-293.
 18. Duffor, C.W and E. Becker (1964). Public Water Supplies of 100 Large Cities in the US Geological Survey. *Water Supply Paper*, pp. 364-369.
 19. Twort, A. C., M. F. Law and F. W. Crowley (1985). *Water Supply*. 3rd Edition, Edward Arnold Int'l Publisher, Hong Kong
 20. Adeodu, A. O., I. A. Daniyan and A. S. Yusuff (2013). Assessment of Soil, Water and Plant Pollution by Heavy Metals from Petroleum and Petrochemical Companies in Nigeria. *Int. Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*. 4(7) 2401- 2412.
 21. Ipinmoroti, K. O., O. Olaofe and Adeyinwo (1997). Interrelationships of Heavy Metal Concentration in Water, Sediments and Fish Sample from Coastal Area. *African Journal of Science*. 1(1): 55-61
 22. Tennant, D. R. (1981). *Environmental Health Criteria*. 17 Manganese W. H. O Programme on Chemical Safety, Geneva.

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